

Solid-supported chiral organocatalysts: Methods, platforms, and applications in asymmetric synthesis

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Organocatalysis
Solid supports
Immobilization
Polymer-supported catalysts
Silica-supported catalysis
Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs)
Heterogeneous catalysis
Continuous flow chemistry
Enantioselectivity

ABSTRACT

Over the past two decades, asymmetric organocatalysis has emerged as a prominent field in synthetic organic chemistry, providing access to a diverse range of valuable chiral compounds through the use of small chiral organic molecules as catalysts. In homogeneous systems, organocatalysts showed remarkable selectivity and efficiency in numerous asymmetric reactions. However, the limitations of homogeneous organocatalysis, such as high catalyst loading, challenging recovery, and potential catalyst degradation, have led to the development of heterogeneous alternatives. Immobilized organocatalysts, which are covalently anchored onto solid supports, address these issues by improving certain catalyst properties, such as stability and reusability. The spatial arrangement of the catalyst on the solid supports can be tailored in order to enhance reactivity and enantioselectivity. This review highlights the significant advancements in immobilized organocatalysts applied to enantioselective synthesis over the past decade, discussing advances in silica-, polymer-, and magnetic nanoparticle-supported organocatalysts, with an emphasis on catalytic performance and reusability. Lastly, some perspectives on the area of supported organocatalysts are provided.

1. Introduction

Chiral organocatalysis, employing small organic molecules, has become a prominent and diverse strategy in the synthesis of enantiomerically enriched compounds, besides transition metal and enzymatic catalysis. Since the early 2000s, chiral organocatalysis has evolved as an independent area of catalysis undergoing a rapid expansion in enantioselective synthesis [1,2], which provides valuable molecules in various fields, including the pharmaceutical, agrochemical industry, and materials science.

The advantages of this approach lie in its ability to operate without the need for transition metals, making it environmentally friendly and cost-effective. Furthermore, many organocatalyzed reactions proceed under mild conditions, delivering excellent enantioselectivities [3–11]. Additionally, organocatalysts often exhibit high stability across a range of media, including water [12–15]. Moreover, their structure can be easily modified, enabling the development of more selective and efficient catalytic systems [16–18].

The strength of organocatalysis lies in its ability to operate through diverse activation modes. Covalent organocatalysis, as a prominent class within organocatalysis, uses proline, diphenylprolinol derivatives, or

imidazolidinones to activate carbonyl compounds via *enamine* or *iminium* intermediates (Fig. 1A). In contrast, carbonyl compounds can be activated through polarity-reversal (*umpolung*) strategy using *N*-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) derived from imidazolium-, triazolium-, or thiazolium-based salts (Fig. 1B).

Conversely, hydrogen-bonding catalysis, using (thio)urea, and squaramide derivatives of cinchona alkaloids, relies on non-covalent interactions between the catalyst and Lewis basic substrates in the transition state (Fig. 1C).

Similarly, chiral phosphoric acids (CPAs), typically based on BINOL, VAPOL, or SPINOL frameworks, act as Brønsted acids to promote stereocontrolled transformation via proton transfer, generating reactive intermediates (Fig. 1D).

Despite significant progress in enantioselective synthesis, homogeneous organocatalysis faces limitations that hinder its broader industrial application. Since most organocatalysts operate in a homogeneous phase, their separation from reaction media and reuse can be challenging, leading to increased costs and waste generation [19–22]. Additionally, high catalyst loadings (5–30 mol%) are often required to achieve effective transformations, limiting the economic viability of organocatalysis for large-scale production [23–25].

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115518>

Received 25 June 2025; Received in revised form 5 August 2025; Accepted 13 August 2025

Available online 21 August 2025

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To address these issues, the immobilization of organocatalysts onto various solid supports has emerged as a promising strategy [26,27]. This approach combines the high selectivity of homogeneous systems with the advantages of heterogeneous materials, such as reusability and easier recovery. In addition, solid-supported catalysts are well-suited for continuous flow systems, offering enhanced process scalability and cost efficiency, which makes them attractive for industrial applications [20, 22,28–30].

With the growing utility and interest in supported organocatalysts, the number of published reviews has increased rapidly [15,20,22,25,27, 28,31–34]. This review primarily aims to highlight advances in the field of immobilized organocatalysts over the past ten years, while also drawing attention to selected earlier achievements in this research area. The focus will be on recent progress in immobilized organocatalysts, with particular emphasis on enantioselective transformations catalyzed by covalently tethered chiral organocatalysts on diverse solid supports, including silica, polymers, and magnetic nanoparticles. Key activation modes, including aminocatalysis, hydrogen-bond catalysis, and Brønsted acid/base catalysis, will be discussed. Furthermore, the review will address the application of these systems in the synthesis of selected bioactive compounds and their implementation in continuous flow processes.

2. Solid supports for organocatalysis

Over the years, a wide range of solid supports has been recognized and employed to develop heterogeneous organocatalysts. In addition to

well-established materials suitable for chiral organocatalyst anchoring, such as silica, polymers, or magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs), other unconventional materials have also been explored. For instance, textile materials have been employed as low-cost and practical supports, as demonstrated in the immobilization of cinchona-derived sulfonamides for the desymmetrization of anhydrides with alcohols [35]. Similarly, a squaramide-cinchonine organocatalyst anchored to commercial porous glass beads has been applied in asymmetric conjugate additions [36]. The choice of support plays a crucial role, offering specific advantages and limitations that affect catalyst performance, stability, and recyclability.

2.1. Silica

Among the various solid supports used in heterogeneous catalysis, silica stands out as the most widely used material due to its high surface area, thermal stability, and well-established surface chemistry. Its surface silanol groups enable robust covalent anchoring of organocatalysts but may also contribute to catalyst deactivation or reduced selectivity [22,37]. Based on the structural features, several distinct forms of silica can be identified.

a) **Amorphous silica (Non-porous silica)** is inexpensive and rich in reactive silanol groups, yet its low surface area limits catalyst loading.

Fig. 1. Selected examples of catalysts and reaction modes used in enantioselective organocatalysis.

- b) **Fumed silica (Aerosil)**, also non-porous, but provides a high surface area owing to its fine particle size and good dispersibility; however, the control over the pore size remains limited.
- c) **Mesoporous silica**, characterized by pores ranging from 2 to 50 nm and a high surface area, offers a tunable structure, enabling high catalyst loading and excellent diffusion of substrates. Additionally, a more defined morphology enhances the reproducibility in preparation, although synthesis and surfactant removal can be time- and cost-demanding [38,39].
- d) **Silica gel**, in contrast, with its irregular pore structure, is less uniform but remains a low-cost platform for the catalyst immobilization [40].
- e) **Silica nanoparticles (NPs)** with colloidal or structured particles with defined size (10–100 nm) provide high surface area and excellent dispersity. On the other hand, aggregation or leaching can be taken into consideration [41].

2.2. Polymeric supports

As versatile platforms in heterogeneous catalysis, polymeric supports are often employed to anchor organocatalysts due to their tunable porosity, polarity, and density of functional groups. However, these advantages are often accompanied by challenges, such as limited mechanical stability, diffusional constraints, and swelling behavior, which can negatively affect the catalyst performance [42]. Based on the structural characteristic, polymeric supports can be categorized into three general classes.

- a) **Cross-linked polystyrene resins** are robust and widely used frameworks for catalyst anchoring due to their ease of functionalization and commercial availability [43].
- b) **Linear soluble polymers (e.g., polyethylene glycol, PEG)** exhibiting high solubility in organic solvents with easy recovery and recyclability via precipitation. This enables their reuse in “homogeneous-like” applications, which make them particularly attractive in such settings [44].
- c) **Functionalized copolymers** that enable the fine-tuning of polarity and porosity through controlled synthesis. However, their preparation can be laborious, and maintaining consistency across batches may be challenging [45].

2.3. Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs)

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) have emerged as a promising platform for organocatalyst immobilization, offering a high surface area, along with facile accessibility of catalytic sites, and with easy separation via an external magnetic field. This feature can be attractive, especially for continuous flow applications. However, challenges such as particle aggregation, limited functionalization density, and the necessity for robust surface coatings to prevent leaching require careful catalyst design [46,47]. These supports can be classified based on structural architecture and surface composition as follows:

- a) **Bare MNPs** composed of iron oxides (e.g. Fe₃O₄ or γ-Fe₂O₃) are simple and cost-effective supports, but as a drawback, limited stability towards oxidation and reduced surface functionalization restricts them from further applications in complex catalytic utilization [48,49].
- b) **Core-shell MNPs** are composed of a magnetic core coated with a shell, which enhances their stability with functional groups, enabling the covalent anchoring of catalysts [42]. Based on the shell composition, **silica-coated MNPs** or **polymer-coated MNPs** can be recognized as possessing all qualities related to silica and polymer supports.
- c) **Porous MNPs** are designed to enhance surface area, allowing efficient mass transfer and higher catalyst loading [50].

Ultimately, the support must therefore be selected to balance catalytic efficiency, stability, and ease of recovery, depending on the specific application.

3. Silica-based supports

Early attempts to immobilize organocatalysts onto solid materials, including silica, trace back to the origins of enantioselective organocatalysis. The popularity of solid support, attributed to the presence of silanol groups, enables covalent bonding with various organocatalysts through suitable linkers/spacers [51]. Immobilization typically proceeds through hydrolysis and condensation of alkoxy-silanes-functionalized linkers, forming a stable covalent bond with hydroxyl groups, which are densely distributed on the silica surface. Additionally, the thermal stability, high surface area, and the versatility of silica morphologies contribute to the popularity of using this support in the synthesis of heterogeneous organocatalysts. Pioneering work in this area was disclosed by Han et al. in 2004, who reported a study on silica gel-supported bis-cinchona alkaloid-promoted asymmetric desymmetrization of *meso*-cyclic anhydrides [52]. Since then, numerous studies have been conducted on various organocatalysts tethered to the surface of the silica [31].

3.1. Aminocatalysis

Aminocatalysis represents one of the most extensively studied applications of silica-immobilized organocatalysts, where chiral secondary amines represent the most commonly employed catalytic systems for heterogeneous applications, particularly on silica-based supports. In this context, the aldol reaction is often used as a benchmark to evaluate the catalytic activity of silica-supported chiral secondary amines. In 2014, He and co-workers developed a heterogenized (*S*)-proline organocatalyst by grafting it onto mesoporous silica containing alternating hydrophobic/hydrophilic blocks (HHBs) [53]. The authors reported a four-step synthesis sequence, starting with the *N*-Boc protection of hydroxyproline (**1**), followed by derivatization of the hydroxyl group. The key step of the synthesis was thiol-ene coupling between the chiral catalyst precursor **3** and the mercaptopropyl-functionalized mesoporous silica (**4**). Subsequent Boc deprotection afforded the desired immobilized catalyst **I** (Scheme 1).

The supported organocatalyst effectively promoted a Knoevenagel–Michael cascade reaction between isatin (**5**), malononitrile (**6**), and acetone (**7**), affording the corresponding product **8** in 85 % yield and up to 91 % ee (Scheme 2A). In addition, the same catalyst provided an aldol reaction in water under reduced catalyst loading (0.63 mol%), giving the product **11a** with up to 95 % ee for *anti*-isomer and 81 % ee for *syn*-isomer. Notably, authors demonstrated that the corresponding reaction was difficult to accomplish using the homogeneous catalyst counterpart. The same reaction with ethyl-2-oxoacetate (**10b**) required higher catalyst loading of **I** (6.7 mol%) but gave comparable selectivity when affording the product **11b** (Scheme 2B).

The same aldol reaction was also employed by Pleixats et al. to assess the performance of proline sulfonamide-functionalized silica catalyst **II**, showing good conversion and moderate to good stereoselectivities (up to 90:10 dr, 94 ee) [54]. Notably, the same catalytic system promoted the synthesis of the Wieland-Miescher ketone (WMK, **13a**) via an intramolecular aldol condensation of ketone **12a** in up to 76 % yield, albeit with only low enantioselectivity (36 % ee) (Scheme 3). Authors reported that the catalyst immobilization generally led to reduced catalytic activity and selectivity across examined transformations.

Aldol reactions were also employed to evaluate the catalytic performance of mono-silylated proline-valinol amides anchored to mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN), which demonstrated efficiency comparable to their homogeneous counterparts, delivering products with up to 90:10 dr and 86 % ee [55]. In a related approach, (*S*)-proline-based catalysts bearing a 1,2,4-triazole moiety and tethered to a

Scheme 1. Synthetic route for the preparation of silica-supported *L*-proline catalyst (I).

Scheme 2. A) Knoevenagel–Michael cascade reaction of isatin, malononitrile, and acetone; B) Direct aldol reaction of cyclohexanone with aldehydes in aqueous media.

Scheme 3. Intramolecular enantioselective aldol reaction with triketone **12a** catalyzed with organosilica-proline catalyst II.

mesoporous silica scaffold were utilized in aldol reactions between ketones and aryl aldehydes or isatine derivatives. While high yields were achieved, only moderate diastereo- and enantioselectivities were observed [56].

Continuous flow systems have also been explored for silica-supported chiral secondary amines. Silica-immobilized pyrrolidine was employed as a stationary phase in HPLC for the enantioselective conjugate addition of cyclohexanone and (*E*)- β -nitrostyrene, affording high stereoselectivity (93:7 dr, 86 % ee) but low yield (up

to 24 %) [57]. In another study, the immobilized secondary amine Ley-Arvidsson-Yamamoto catalyst (III), along with a series of diphenylprolinol derivatives – non-protected (IV) or functionalized with TMS (V) or TBS (VI) groups – were investigated in small-scale continuous flow reactions using a microreactor integrated with on-chip chiral HPLC/MS detection (Fig. 2) [58]. The microreactor performance was evaluated in the stereoselective Mannich reaction using PMP-protected aldimine and in the amination of aldehyde with dibenzyl azodicarboxylate. However, the TMS-protected catalyst exhibited poor enantioselectivity, likely due to cleavage of the TMS group caused by interactions with surface silanols on the silica support.

In addition to prolinol-type catalysts, silica-immobilized

Fig. 2. Immobilized Ley-Arvidsson-Yamamoto (III) and other diphenylprolinols (IV–VI) employed in small-scale continuous flow Mannich and amination reactions.

imidazolidinone derivatives have also been prepared and studied. These catalysts were successfully employed in the diastereoselective Diels-Alder reaction between cyclopentadiene and α,β -unsaturated cinnamic aldehyde under continuous-flow conditions [59,60]. In both studies, the authors demonstrated improved catalytic performance under continuous-flow conditions compared to the batch process.

Besides secondary amines, chiral primary amine-based catalysts supported on silica have also gained attention for enantioselective transformations. In 2019, Villani's research group introduced silica-tethered primary amine derived from cinchona alkaloid quinine (VII)

[61]. Catalyst tethered to silica, along with supported-achiral acid co-catalyst, was applied in the conjugate addition of cyclic ketones to (*E*)- β -nitrostyrene under both batch and continuous flow conditions, delivering selectivities comparable to those achieved with the corresponding homogeneous catalytic system. Notably, the enantioselective synthesis of warfarin (**16**) from 4-hydroxycoumarin (**14**) and 4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one (**15**) was achieved in 97 % yield and with 78 % ee under a continuous flow setup (Scheme 4). Further expanding the use of silica-supported primary amines in continuous flow conditions, mesoporous silica support was utilized as a support for peptide-based organocatalyst (*R*)-Pro-(*S*)-Pro-(*S*)-Glu [62]. This hybrid catalyst enabled the enantioselective conjugated addition of *n*-butanal to β -nitrostyrene, demonstrating improved activity of the material using silica with larger pores compared to silica with small pores due to enhanced substrate accessibility. On the other hand, a slight decrease in the enantioselectivity of the reaction was observed compared to the homogeneous system.

3.2. H-Bonding catalysis

Building on the use of covalent organocatalysts, the concept of hydrogen-bonding (H-bonding) catalysis has also been investigated in silica-supported organocatalysts. For instance, in 2014, Corma et al. developed a novel method for the direct preparation of GABA analogues, including (*R*)-phenibut, (*R*)-rolipram, (*R*)-baclofen, and (*S*)-pregabalin via multicomponent reaction of aldehydes (**10**), nitromethane (**2**), and malonates (**3**) (Fig. 3) under batch conditions [63].

The reaction proceeded through an aldol condensation followed by stereoselective conjugate addition to afford the chiral compound **19**, catalyzed by a hybrid organic–inorganic solid catalyst **VIII** bearing quinidine thiourea moiety (Scheme 5). Following heterogeneous hydrogenation of the nitro group to the primary amine, triggered spontaneous amide cyclization, and subsequent thermal decarboxylation of the ester moiety afforded the final compound **20** in yields ranging from 38 % to 63 % with high optical purity (up to 97 % ee). Moreover, the catalyst was successfully recyclable, and the presented methodology could be scaled up to yield 1 g of the product.

3.3. Brønsted acid (BA) and Brønsted base (BB) catalysis

Silica has also served to immobilize chiral Brønsted acid catalysts. In 2020, Ishihara and co-workers reported a silica-supported ammonium binaphthyl 2,2'-disulfonates (BINSate) to promote enantioselective Friedel-Craft-type double aminoalkylation of *N*-benzoyl or *N*-methylpyrrole with aldimines [64]. The resulting heterogeneous catalyst **IX** exhibited higher catalytic performance – both in terms of reactivity and selectivity – compared to its homogeneous BINSa analogue. The corresponding *C*₂-triamines (**23**) were isolated in up to 96 % yields with up to 99 % ee (Scheme 6A). Notably, the heterogeneous catalyst **IX** was reusable over three cycles without any loss of catalytic performance. In 2024, Schneider and co-workers developed a modular synthesis of

silica-immobilized chiral phosphoric acids **X**, which were successfully applied to chiral reactions under both batch and continuous flow conditions. The resulting catalytic materials **Xa-b** exhibited excellent stability and performance in the Mannich reaction between aldehydes **10**, *p*-methoxyaniline (**24**), and cyclic silyl dienolate **25**, as well as in the stereoselective transfer hydrogenation of preformed 2,3-substituted quinolines **29**. In both cases, the desired products were delivered in high yields and stereoselectivities over 23 h of continuous flow operation (Scheme 6B-C) [65].

Silica-supported version of Lambert catalyst – chiral cyclopropenimine super-base (**XI**) – was introduced by Massi and co-workers in 2021 through the immobilization of a 2,3-bisaminocyclopropenium salt precursor **31** (Scheme 7A) [66]. The resulting catalyst exhibited excellent performance in the conjugate addition of glycine imine **33** to various electron-deficient olefins **34** under batch conditions, affording products in yields up to 92 % with up to 98 % ee (Scheme 7B). The silica-immobilized Lambert catalyst demonstrated reactivity and induction of enantioselectivity comparable to those of its homogeneous counterparts. The system was also adapted for continuous flow, maintaining high enantioselectivity (98 % ee) and conversion (>95 %) over 24 h, though prolonged use led to reduced catalyst productivity.

4. Polymer-based supports

Polymers are a widely used class of supports to anchor organocatalysts due to a tunable polymer backbone, which enables precise control over the spatial arrangement of catalytic sites and easy incorporation of functional groups. This modularity facilitates the optimization of catalysts for specific transformations. The ability of polymers to swell in suitable solvents may also improve the substrate access, and their mechanical flexibility makes them compatible with packed-bed flow systems. Additionally, lower polymer density often results in enhanced mass transfer compared to inorganic supports. However, diffusion limitations can occur in densely cross-linked matrices. Notably, some polymers are prone to degrade under harsh reaction conditions, limiting their use in more demanding setups [42].

4.1. Aminocatalysis

Among various catalytic strategies, aminocatalysis is the most widely applied mode of organocatalysis anchored to polymeric supports. In 2016, Pericàs and co-workers pioneered in the immobilization of second-generation MacMillan imidazolidin-4-one catalyst onto slightly cross-linked polystyrene (**XII**). This material was applied to catalyze the Friedel-Crafts alkylation of indoles (**36**) with α,β -unsaturated aldehydes **37** [67]. Corresponding products **38** were obtained in 66–79 % yield and up to 93 % ee (Scheme 8A).

Going from batch to flow setup, the same group later developed a polystyrene-supported TBS-protected analogue of the Hayashi-Jørgensen catalyst **XIII** [68]. Initially, the immobilized catalyst was applied in a cascade cyclopropanation reaction of enals (**37**) with

Scheme 4. Conjugated addition reaction catalyzed by silica-immobilized quinine (**VII**) between 4-hydroxycoumarin (**14**) and (*E*)-4-phenylbut-3-en-2-one (**15**) for enantioselective warfarin (**16**) synthesis under continuous flow setup.

Fig. 3. Structures of GABA and its pharmaceutical analogues.

Scheme 6. A) Chiral silica-supported ammonium BINSate (**IX**) catalyzed Friedel-Crafts-type double aminoalkylation reaction; B) Stereoselective Mannich reaction catalyzed by **Xa**; C) Stereoselective synthesis of dihydroquinazolines catalyzed by **Xb**.

dimethyl bromomalonate (**39**) under batch conditions, exhibiting higher catalytic activity than its homogeneous counterpart. Encouraged by these results, heterogenized catalyst **XIII** was successfully implemented

under continuous flow conditions [68]. The resulting material was used to prepare a small library of cyclopropane analogues **40** with up to 96% ee, demonstrating excellent stability without loss of activity (Scheme

Scheme 7. A) Synthesis of the silica-supported cyclopropenimine superbase Lambert catalyst (**XI**); B) Scheme of the conjugate reaction of glycine imine **33** to different acceptors **34** catalyzed by immobilized Lambert catalyst (**XI**) under batch conditions.

Scheme 8. A) Friedel-Craft alkylation of indoles catalyzed by immobilized 2nd-generation MacMillan catalyst **XII**; B) Cyclopropanation catalyzed by polystyrene-supported TBS-protected Hayashi-Jørgensen catalyst **XIII** under continuous flow conditions; C) Multigram-scale synthesis of piperidine derivative **42** catalyzed by heterogenized catalyst **XIV** under continuous flow conditions.

8B).

In the subsequent study, a polystyrene-supported *cis*-4-hydroxydiphenylprolinol TBS ether catalyst (**XIV**) was used in the large-scale synthesis of phenylpiperidine derivative **42**, a key intermediate for antidepressant (-)-paroxetine [69]. The four-step process was optimized and integrated into a continuous flow setup. The key enantioselective conjugate addition reaction of dimethyl malonate (**17**) to 4-fluorocinnamaldehyde (**37a**) proceeded smoothly under neat conditions, delivering the chiral substituted aldehyde **41** in 84 % yield with excellent enantiomeric purity (97 % ee). The resulting chiral α -substituted aldehyde **41** was then subjected to a reaction sequence, comprising reductive amination with BH_3 .DMS, lactamization, and final amide/ester reduction. This sequence delivered the corresponding paroxetine building-block **42** on a multigram-per-hour scale with high chemo- and stereoselectivity (Scheme 8C).

In parallel, Zczeński and co-workers reported the total synthesis of (+)-paroxetine and (+)-fexometine using a Wang resin-immobilized Hayashi-Jørgensen catalyst [70]. However, unlike the fully integrated flow synthesis described above, this study did not incorporate all synthetic steps into a continuous sequence, resulting in a less streamlined process.

Enantioselective conjugate addition of aliphatic aldehydes to β -nitrostyrene derivatives catalyzed by immobilized secondary amines has been studied under both batch and continuous flow conditions. In a flow setup, Belder and co-workers developed a glass chip-microreactor system by immobilizing a TMS-protected Hayashi-Jørgensen onto monolithic polystyrene via visible-light-induced polymerization [71]. The resulting catalytic matrix efficiently promoted conjugate addition, providing high distereo- (up to 9:1 dr) and enantiocontrol (up to 90 % ee), as confirmed by integrated HPLC/MS. In parallel, Hayashi and co-workers applied a related strategy in batch mode, employing a polymer-supported diphenylprolinol alkyl ether for the same transformation [72]. To enhance stability over silyl ether analogues, an anthrylmethyl ether-substituted derivative was immobilized on a polystyrene-poly(ethylene glycol) resin via CuAAC click chemistry. The catalyst was used at only 5 mol% loading in water, delivering products in 76 %-94 % yield with excellent stereocontrol (4:1-16:1 dr, and with 90-99 % ee). While enantioselectivity remained consistent over four cycles, conversion declined significantly after the second run.

In 2023, Zhang and co-workers reported a one-step bottom-up immobilization of a chiral MacMillan catalyst using a phenolic-type polymer [73]. The catalyst performed well in the asymmetric

Diels-Alder reaction, delivering the products in the yields ranging from 81 % to 97 % yield with up to 92 % ee for *exo* and up to 93 % ee for *endo* isomers. Moreover, easy recovery by precipitation from hexane and reusability for five cycles were demonstrated, although a gradual decline in enantioselectivity due to partial decomposition was observed.

The asymmetric Mannich reaction has been effectively catalyzed by both chiral secondary and primary amines immobilized on solid supports. He and co-workers developed an immobilization strategy using 2-chlorotriethyl chloride resin to anchor hydroxyproline methyl ester [74]. The resulting polymer-supported catalyst was applied to the asymmetric Mannich-type reaction between 2-aryl-3*H*-indol-3-ones with aldehydes or ketones, yielding chiral C2-quaternary indolin-3-ones in good yields (up to 83 %) with high diastereoselectivity (up to 20:1) and up to 99 % ee under batch conditions. Notably, the catalyst kept high stereocontrol over four reaction cycles.

In a complementary study, Pericàs and co-workers in 2014, demonstrated the first use of a primary amine catalyst immobilized on polystyrene for the *anti*-selective Mannich reaction under both batch and continuous flow conditions [75]. A polystyrene-supported threonine derivative (**XV**) tethered via a 1,2,3-triazole linker catalyzed the three-component *anti*-Mannich reaction of hydroxyacetone (**43**), anilines (**24**), and various aldehydes (**10**). The catalyst afforded *anti*-Mannich products **44** in up to 96 % yield with up to 95 % ee under batch conditions. Moreover, the catalyst demonstrated excellent recyclability, achieving an accumulated turnover number (TON) greater than 20 – significantly higher than those of comparable homogeneous reference catalysts, which exhibited TONs in the range of 3 – 5. Continuous flow experiments further confirmed high catalytic activity, as demonstrated by the production of diverse Mannich products **44**. A small library of five derivatives **44** was prepared sequentially in 69–94 % yield, with diastereoselectivity ranging from 89:11–92:8 dr and with high enantioselectivity (80–96 % ee) (Scheme 9).

Building on the utility of immobilized chiral primary amines in aminocatalysis, in 2015 the Puglisi group developed chiral cinchona-derived primary amines covalently anchored on polystyrene (PS) and poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) supports [76]. Both catalysts effectively promoted the enantioselective conjugate addition of α -branched saturated aldehydes to β -nitrostyrene. Moreover, a synthesis of anticoagulant warfarin – a benchmark reaction previously demonstrated by Villani et al [61]. – was successfully promoted with the PS-supported 9-amino-*epi*-quinine. The reaction between 4-hydroxycoumarin (**14**) and *trans*-4-phenyl-3-buten-2-one (**15**) afforded product **16** in 83 % yield with 93 % ee.

Enones have also been employed as electrophiles in conjugate addition reactions with various carbon nucleophiles, under catalysis with 9-amino(9-deoxy)*epi*-quinine tethered to a polystyrene support, in both batch and continuous flow systems [77]. Prepared immobilized catalyst showed similar activity in terms of the yield and enantioselectivity compared to the homogeneous analogue. As a further development, Robinson annulation, a cascade process, involving an initial conjugate addition of diketones to enones followed by an intramolecular aldol condensation, was employed by Pericàs's research group to assess the catalytic performance of heterogenized organocatalyst **XVI** based on a polystyrene-supported version of Luo's diamine in both batch and

continuous flow system [78]. This methodology served as an example of a desymmetrization strategy successfully applied to prochiral cyclic diketones (**45**, **46**), enabling the effective sequential synthesis of a diverse library of Hajos–Parrish (HPK, **47**) and Wieland–Miescher (WMK, **13**) ketones under continuous flow conditions, obtained in high yields and enantiomeric purities (Scheme 10).

In a further development in desymmetrization, Szöllösi's group reported enantioselective desymmetrization of maleimides with isobutryl aldehydes using a PS-supported chiral diamine catalyst [79]. The system delivered products with up to 97 % ee, but recyclability was limited due to declining activity after three cycles. Catalyst deactivation was attributed to leaching (confirmed by SEM) and irreversible side reactions between primary amines and excess aldehyde.

4.2. H-Bonding catalysis

Non-covalent catalysis has also been explored in polymer-supported organocatalysts. In 2015, the Pericàs's group reported a modular, polymer-supported catalyst **XVII** substituted with a chiral bifunctional thiourea scaffold, employing a streamlined synthetic strategy that enabled direct attachment to the polymer backbone without the need for a linker or spacer [80]. The catalyst was applied to the enantioselective α -amination of cyclic 1,3-oxoesters with azodicarboxylates under both batch and continuous flow conditions. For example, α -amination of ethyl oxocyclopentanecarboxylate (**48**) proceeded with 71 % yield and 93 % ee over 7.5 h (Scheme 11A). In another example, asymmetric α -amination of 2-oxindols (**51**) with diethyl azodicarboxylates (**49b**) was carried out using quinidine-supported catalyst **XVIII**, affording the corresponding products (**52**) in up to 95 % yield and 95 % ee (Scheme 11B) [81]. The results were comparable to those obtained with non-immobilized counterpart. Notably, the supported catalyst exhibited exceptional stability under batch conditions, maintaining its catalytic performance over 5300 h of operation.

Additionally, imines, as valuable building blocks in the synthesis of biologically active molecules, have been utilized in polymer-supported, catalyzed transformations. In 2016, Pedrosa and co-workers reported the aza-Henry reaction of aldimines protected with *tert*-butyloxycarbonyl (Boc) group **53** with nitroalkanes **54** catalyzed by a polymer-supported chiral thiourea **XIX** derived from (*S*)-valine and commercially available 1,6-hexanediamine as a spacer [82]. The prepared catalyst provided products *anti*-**55** in up to 94 % yields with enantioselectivity up to 88 % ee under batch conditions (Scheme 12A). Notably, the generality of the catalytic system was demonstrated on the conjugate addition of oxoesters and diesters to nitroolefins under neat conditions, exhibiting superior reactivity and stereoselectivity compared to its homogeneous counterparts. Catalyst recyclability was successfully demonstrated over three reaction cycles, while maintaining stereoselectivity.

The same research group also utilized isatin-based ketimines (**56**) in enantioselective aza-Friedel-Crafts reaction of 1- and 2-naphthols under PS-supported cinchona alkaloid catalysis [83]. The PS-supported hydroquinine-derived thiourea catalyst **XX** provided the corresponding products in high yields (64–92 %) and excellent enantiomeric ratios (up to 96 % ee) under batch conditions – comparable to the results

Scheme 9. Continuous flow experiment used in the synthesis of *anti*-Mannich products **44** catalyzed by threonine-based primary amine PS-supported organocatalyst **XV**.

Scheme 10. Continuous flow asymmetric Robinson annulation for structurally diverse diketones (**45**, **46**) under catalysis of **XVI**.

Scheme 11. A) Enantioselective α-amination of ethyl oxocyclopentanecarboxylate (**48**) catalyzed by **XVII** under continuous flow conditions; B) Enantioselective α-amination of 2-oxindols (**51**) catalyzed by **XVIII** under batch setup.

Scheme 12. A) Stereoselective aza-Henry reaction of aldimines **53** and nitroalkanes **54** catalyzed by **XIX** under batch setup; B) Enantioselective aza-Friedel-Crafts reaction of 1-naphthol (**57**) with ketimines **56a-b** catalyzed by **XX** under continuous flow conditions.

obtained with the homogeneous catalyst. Notably, the application of the catalyst into a continuous flow setup was successfully demonstrated on a multi-gram scale reaction of 1-naphthol (**57**) with ketimines **56a-b**. Corresponding products **58a** and **58b** were obtained in 80 % yield with high enantiomeric purities 88 % ee and 94 % ee, respectively. Additionally, a considerable decrease in the reaction time to achieve full conversion was observed (residence time 10.3 min), which was significantly faster than in the three-hour batch experiment (Scheme 12B).

As a biodegradable alternative to synthetic polymers, chitosan has been used as the solid support for chiral thiourea, as reported by Adrés [84]. The material was evaluated in enantioselective aza-Henry reaction

under batch conditions, showing reusability over five consecutive cycles. The same support was later used to anchor the urea moiety, resulting in a material that has been active in enantioselective cyanosilylation, hydrazone addition, and Friedel-Crafts reactions, though with modest enantioselectivity (up to 28 % ee) [85].

Squaramides, an important class of hydrogen-bonding catalysts, have also been immobilized on polymer supports, such as Wang resin, as reported by Pericàs and co-workers [86]. The resulting catalyst **XXI** was applied in a sequential continuous-flow stereoselective two-step synthesis of pyranonaphthoquinones (**61**), involving Michael reaction/oxa-Michael cyclization. Corresponding products were isolated

in yields ranging from 61 % to 83 % with excellent diastereoselectivity (up to 99:1 dr) and enantioselectivity (up to 98 % ee) (Scheme 13A).

Kupai and co-workers reported the immobilization of cinchona-based squaramide organocatalysts **XXII** on poly(glycidyl methacrylate) microspheres [87]. The prepared catalyst, tethered to the microsphere via a linker attached to the quinoline moiety, was evaluated in the conjugate addition of pentane-2,4-dione (**62**) to *trans*- β -nitrostyrene (**63**), delivering the product **64** in 84 % yield and 96 % ee under batch conditions. Recyclability with preserved enantioselectivity was confirmed over five consecutive cycles; however, a slight decrease in the yield was observed in the final two rounds (Scheme 13B).

4.3. Brønsted acid (BA) and Brønsted base (BB) catalysis

Brønsted acid catalysis was also successfully applied using polymer-supported organocatalysts. Pericàs and co-workers, active in this field, reported the synthesis of a PS-supported BINOL-derived chiral phosphoric acid (CPA) catalyst in 2014 [88]. The prepared catalyst was effective in the enantioselective Friedel-Crafts reaction of indols and sulfonylimines under continuous-flow conditions, providing corresponding products in high yields (44–94 %) with enantioselectivity up to 98 % ee. Later, in 2016, they immobilized the widely used TRIP phosphoric acid on a PS support, and the prepared catalytic resin **XXIII** was successfully evaluated in the enantioselective allylic alkylation of aldehydes **10** with allylboronic esters **65** in a batch [89]. High yields of the desired products and excellent enantioselectivity demonstrated high effectiveness of the material, comparable to its homogeneous counterpart. The effectiveness was further confirmed over 18 cycles in a batch and after 28 h of operation in continuous flow conditions, yielding 4.6 g (90 %) of allylated product **66** (Scheme 14A). The same catalytic system **XXIII** was later evaluated under both batch and continuous flow conditions for the enantioselective spirocyclization via the Pictet-Spengler reaction between trimptamines **67** and isatines **68** [90]. The authors demonstrated that the immobilized catalyst provided enantioselectivities comparable to those achieved with the homogeneous TRIP catalyst. Under the flow conditions, a small library of the spiroindolones **69** was synthesized in generally high yields and up to 99 % ee after recrystallization (Scheme 14B). Additionally, the same immobilized TRIP catalyst was employed for the desymmetrization of *meso*-1,3-diones **70** via an intramolecular aldol condensation, delivering products in up to 92 %

yield with 92 % ee in a batch setup (Scheme 14C), and exhibiting stable catalytic activity over nine cycles [91]. Their continuing effort in desymmetrization led to the development of a method for the enantioselective desymmetrization of 3,3-disubstituted oxetanes [92]. Reaction catalyzed by 1,1'-spirobiindane-7,7'-diol (SPINOL)-based chiral phosphoric acids immobilized on cross-linked PS support via the 4,4'-positions. The prepared catalyst **XXIV** promoted the reaction of 3-substituted oxetanes **71** with 3-mercaptobenzothiazoles **72**, yielding up to 92 % and with high enantiomeric purity (up to 99 % ee) under batch conditions. Notably, this performance surpassed that of the corresponding homogeneous catalyst. Significantly, a successful transfer to continuous flow conditions was demonstrated by sequential preparation of a library of seventeen chiral diols **73**, showing excellent scalability and unlimited recyclability without any loss of efficiency (Scheme 14D). In 2022, You, Tu, and Gu reported the synthesis of BINOL-derived CPAs bearing anthracene units at the 3,3'-positions – serving both as steric directing groups and as a connection to a porous polymer network [93]. The prepared catalyst was applied in enantioselective dearomatization reactions, including the transfer hydrogenation of 2-phenylquinolines and dearomatative amination of β -naphthols with diethyl azodicarboxylates (DEAD) under batch conditions, affording excellent yields (up to 98 %) and enantioselectivities (up to 99 % ee), which were maintained over 10 catalytic cycles. The performance closely matched that of the corresponding homogeneous catalyst in terms of both yield and stereoselectivity.

Brønsted bases were also immobilized on polymeric supports and applied in asymmetric catalysis. Pericàs and co-workers disclosed a cascade annulation of alkylidene pyrazolones **74** or thiazolones **75** with phenylacetic acids (**76**), catalyzed by a polystyrene-supported chiral isothiourea **XXV** [94]. The method provides access to dihydropyranopyrazolones **77** and dihydropyranothiazolones **78**, with yields up to 91 % as nearly enantiopure compounds (up to 99 % ee, Scheme 15A). The catalyst exhibited higher stereoselectivity compared to its homogeneous counterpart and demonstrated excellent reusability over 11 cycles. Additionally, the catalyst was effectively applied in the continuous flow system.

Later, Pericàs and Smith jointly reported a four-step synthesis of a PS-supported isothiourea catalyst **XXVI** for the kinetic resolution of a racemic mixture of secondary alcohols [95]. The immobilized catalyst demonstrated efficiency comparable to its homogeneous counterparts.

Scheme 13. A) Stereoselective sequential synthesis of pyranonaphthoquinones **61** under continuous flow conditions; B) Reusability of immobilized catalyst **XXII** in conjugate addition of **62** to **63**.

Scheme 14. A) Enantioselective allylic alkylation of **10** with **65** catalyzed by PS-supported TRIP-CPA (**XXIII**) under continuous flow system; B) Pictet-Spengler reaction between trimptamines **67** and isatines **68** catalyzed by PS-supported TRIP-CPA (**XXIII**) under batch; C) Desymmetrization of *meso*-diones **70** catalyzed by PS-supported TRIP-CPA (**XXIII**) under batch; D) Desymmetrization of 3,3-disubstituted oxetanes **71** catalyzed by PS-supported SPA (**XXIV**).

Scheme 15. A) PS-supported chiral isothioure-catalyzed (**XXV**) synthesis of dihydropyranopyrazolones (**77**) and dihydropyranothiazolones (**78**) under batch conditions; B) Sequential continuous flow kinetic resolution of secondary alcohols **79**.

Under batch conditions, only 1 mol% of the catalyst was sufficient for effective resolution of various alcohols, affording selectivity factors up to > 600, and retained effectiveness was proven over 15 cycles. Moreover, a sequential resolution of nine different alcohols **79** was demonstrated with no cross-contamination and on a large-scale synthesis (almost 29 mmol) under continuous flow kinetic resolutions (Scheme 15B).

Moreover, the opposite enantiomer of immobilized isothioure **XXVI** was effectively applied by Smith and co-workers in the enantioselective annulation of various phenacetyl-derived heterocycles. These included (benzo)thiazoles, benzoxazoles, and benzoimidazoles, which reacted with α,β -unsaturated anhydrides under continuous flow conditions to afford the corresponding lactams in high yields and up to 94 % ee [96].

Additionally, the chiral reduction of ketimines has been developed

under polymer-supported Brønsted base conditions, utilizing HSiCl₃ as a hydrogenation agent. Benaglia and Puglisi disclosed an enantioselective reduction of ketimines catalyzed by PS-supported chiral *N*-picolinoyl imidazolidinones, demonstrating high enantioselectivities up to 98 % ee across a broad substrate scope with 1 mol% loading of the catalyst under batch conditions, showing similar catalytic activity to the homogeneous counterpart [97]. However, under flow conditions, a gradual decline in stereoselectivity was observed, likely due to degradation of the imidazolidinone unit.

In 2024, García-Verdugo et al. described the same reaction catalyzed with polymer-supported (*S*)-proline-derived *N*-carbonyl amides under a continuous flow system, where the catalyst delivered higher enantiocontrol (88 % ee) compared to the batch process (70 % ee) [98].

Another interesting immobilization strategy was reported by Ma and

co-workers. In this study, a general method was developed for covalently anchoring various chiral organocatalysts to mesoporous polystyrene nanospheres via a tandem chloromethylation/Friedel-Crafts alkylation process (Scheme 16) [99]. The strategy allowed direct immobilization of TRIP phosphoric acid (XXVII) and *p*re-NHCs (XXVIII). Additionally, Boc-protected MacMillan catalysts, diphenylprolinol TMS ethers, and cinchona-based amines, after removal of the Boc group, afforded corresponding immobilized catalysts XXIX-XXXI. These catalysts demonstrated high enantiocontrol of reactions, often matching or exceeding their homogeneous counterparts.

5. Magnetic nanoparticle-based supports

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) have emerged as a valuable support for chiral organocatalysts due to their distinctive properties, including a large surface area, easy functionalization, and efficient magnetic separation, which eliminates the need for filtration or centrifugation [32, 33]. However, magnetic interactions can lead to nanoparticle aggregation, which may reduce catalytic activity [100]. Moreover, catalyst leaching and limitations in magnetic separation under large-scale or harsh conditions can affect their practical usability. Typically, magnetic core materials, such as iron oxides, are coated with a suitable material, such as silica or functionalized organic layers, which enables covalent anchoring of a variety of organocatalysts.

5.1. Aminocatalysis

Aminocatalysis employing secondary amine catalysts has been implemented in MNP-supported organocatalysts through the synthesis of (*S*)-proline-functionalized MNPs. Safaei-Ghomi and Zahedi evaluated such a catalyst in a three-component Mannich reaction [101], while Muñoz-Espí and co-workers applied it in the aldol reaction [102]. In both studies, the catalysts afforded the corresponding products in good yields and high diastereoselectivities; however, enantioselectivities were not reported.

Also, the enantioselective Friedel-Crafts alkylation of indoles (36) with enals (37) under batch conditions was catalyzed by the second generation of MacMillan imidazolidin-4-one immobilized on Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles via CuAAC reaction [67]. In this comparative study, Pericás and co-workers reported that the magnetic nanoparticle-supported catalyst exhibited lower stability and stereoselectivity compared to its polymer-supported counterpart.

Primary chiral amine, 9-amino(9-deoxy)*epi*-cinchonidine

immobilized on MNPs was successfully applied in the enantioselective aldol reaction of cyclohexanone with various benzaldehyde derivatives, delivering the corresponding aldol products in good yields (36–100 %) and excellent stereoselectivities (*anti/syn* 82–98/18–2 and up to 98 % ee for the *anti* diastereoisomer) [103]. Notably, the immobilized catalyst outperformed its homogeneous counterpart, affording higher yields and stereoselectivities. Additionally, 9-amino(9-deoxy)*epi*-quinidine was tethered to the outer polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) layer of core-shell Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles via a one-pot strategy involving radical thiol-ene click reaction followed by hydrolysis [104]. This catalytic system XXXII was applied to the enantioselective α -amination of various chiral aldehydes with diisopropyl azodicarboxylate (49c, DIAD), affording products 85 in high yields (56–89 %), with excellent diastereo- (*syn/anti* up to 98/2) and enantioselectivities (up to 98 % ee) (Scheme 17). The catalyst was recovered using an external magnetic field and reused over five cycles without significant loss in stereoselectivity.

6. Conclusions and perspectives

Immobilized chiral organocatalysts offer significant advantages, including catalyst reusability and facile separation from reaction mixtures. A variety of supports can be tailored to specific organic catalysts, each providing unique properties. It has been shown that immobilized organocatalysts enable reactions carried out in batch. Moreover, they are compatible with continuous flow systems, which enhances process efficiency and makes them attractive candidates for industrial processes. However, several challenges remain, such as reduced catalytic activity, catalyst leaching, or limited substrate scope caused by steric or diffusional limitations upon immobilization. Additionally, laborious synthetic protocols are needed for preparing immobilized systems, which hinder their broader implementation. It can be expected that future progress will focus on designing modular and robust protocols compatible with the broad scope of organocatalysts to be anchored, as well as the development of more stable and sustainable supports.

Looking ahead, a promising future for advancing immobilized organocatalysts lies in its integration with transition metal catalysis to develop cooperative or synergistic catalytic systems, which remains largely unexplored [105–107]. This hybrid approach could merge the high enantioselectivity of organocatalysis with the broad bond-forming capabilities of metal catalysis, enabling multistep or cascade transformations within a single synthetic operation. This so-called synergistic catalysis will require careful control over catalyst anchoring to prevent

Scheme 16. A) Immobilization strategy involving tandem chloromethylation/F-C reactions to prepare various polymer-supported organocatalysts XXVII-XXXI.

Scheme 17. The stereoselective α -amination of **84** using DIAD (**49c**) catalyzed by Fe₃O₄/PVP@epi-QDNH₂ (**XXXII**).

its deactivation and maintain activity, which can be achieved by using spatially organized supports.

In this context, materials such as mesoporous silica, polymers, and magnetic nanoparticles offer tunable platforms for dual catalyst anchoring. These supports provide control over surface chemistry, porosity, and functionality, making them particularly suitable for heterogeneous applications. Moreover, their integration into continuous flow systems has been already successfully demonstrated showing enhanced performance, scalability, and reusability in a range of catalytic transformations.

Zeolites, meanwhile, represent a promising yet less explored class of materials for organocatalyst immobilization. With their well-defined microporous structures, high thermal stability, and tunable acidity, they are well suited for use in both batch and flow processes. While conventional 3D zeolites may suffer from diffusion limitations — especially with bulky substrates — emerging 2D zeolite architectures, such as delaminated or layered variants, provide greater accessibility to internal surfaces [108–110]. This open structure facilitates better catalyst dispersion and improves substrate–catalyst interactions. When functionalized with catalytic groups, 2D zeolites have shown improved activity and stereoselectivity in asymmetric transformations, combining the advantages of molecular-level confinement with improved mass transport [111].

Beyond traditional supports, two emerging classes of materials are showing great potential for next-generation immobilized organocatalysts. First, Covalent Organic Frameworks (COFs), as porous materials with well-defined crystalline structures and high surface areas, can offer opportunities for designing highly active and selective immobilized organocatalysts. COFs also provide high chemical and thermal stability, making them compatible with a range of solvents and reaction conditions [112–114]. Second, supramolecular host–guest platforms, utilizing reversible interactions such as hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic effects, or coordination, can form catalytic systems through the non-covalent immobilization of organocatalysts within well-defined cavities or networks. These systems offer responsive behavior, when controlled release and recovery of the catalyst can be triggered by external stimuli, enabling recycling of the catalytic function [115]. Together, these directions highlight the growing importance of structurally and functionally sophisticated support systems, where modularity, adaptability, and fine-tuning in catalyst design are becoming key aspects of future development.

Despite the remarkable progress in the academic development of immobilized chiral organocatalysts, their industrial implementations remain scarce. While the benefits of immobilization — such as catalyst recovery, reusability, and potential for continuous flow applications — are well recognized, several fundamental barriers have limited broader use. The key concerns among these are scalability challenges and the cost-effectiveness issues arising from the performance gap caused by catalyst immobilization, which often leads to a loss of activity or

enantiocontrol. In addition, the lack of standardized, modular immobilization platforms that are compatible with a wide range of organocatalysts and reaction types further hampers further industrial utilization. Nevertheless, as the field progresses, the development of modular immobilization protocols, coupled with insights from materials science and catalysis, will be crucial in designing efficient, recyclable, and selective catalytic systems for sustainable and industrially relevant transformations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Martin Kamlar: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Jan Veselý:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the financial support provided by EXPRO project (No. 25–16818X) and ERDF/ESF project TECHSCALE (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587).

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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